

CV template

Annotated Résumé for Research and Innovation (R4RI)-like Narrative CV Template

This annotated CV template aims to illustrate the commonalities of the Résumé for Research and Innovation (R4RI)-like narrative CVs as used by some members of the Joint Funders Group. It includes sections used by other formats, such as the Royal Society's Résumé for Researchers. This example was informed by the R4RI-like narrative CV template synthesis undertaken in January 2022.

Team composition

Team member	Initials	Short role descriptor (max 100 characters)

All funders ask for an applicant's personal details. The majority do not include this specific ask as a section within the CV template as these details are collected elsewhere within the application.

Module 1 – Contributions to the generation of new ideas, tools, methodologies, or knowledge

All ask for an applicant's contribution to the generation of knowledge.

Module 2 – The development of others and maintenance of effective working relationships

All ask an applicant to demonstrate how they have contributed to the development of individuals.

Module 3 – Contributions to the wider research and innovation community

All ask an applicant to demonstrate any contribution to the wider research community.

Module 4 – Contributions to broader research/innovation-users and audiences and towards wider societal benefit

Many ask an applicant to outline contribution to broader society.

Additions

Many provide space for additional information. Some are explicit about what this might include e.g. career breaks.

Personal statement

Some ask for a personal statement/declaration from an applicant.

Version Number	Status	Revision Date	Author(s)	Summary of Changes
1.0	Complete	March 2022	Joint Funders Group	New resource created
2.0	Complete	May 2023	Joint Funders Group	Proof-edited and designed